

Supporting Information for

Synthesis and electronic properties of anthracenyl 5,10-dihydrophenazine derivatives

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1. Materials

Trifluoroacetic acid (99 %) was purchased from Thermo Fisher scientific, 9-bromoanthracene (97 %), pnenazine (95 %), Di-*tert*-butyl dicarbonate (97 %), 4-Dimethylaminopyridine (99 %), Pd(OAc)₂ (99 %) and Pd(TFA)₂ (99 %) were purchased from Fluorochem, Sodium nitrate (98 %) and acetic anhydride (99 %) were purchased from Mikrochem, Tri-*tert*-butylphosphonium tetrafluoroborate (98 %) was purchased from Indagoo, Sodium *tert*-butoxide (97 %) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Toluene and 1,4-dioxane were distilled from sodium–benzophenone ketyl. Silica gel (particle size 35-75 μm) from Sigma Aldrich was used for column chromatography. Thin-layer chromatography was performed on Merck TLC-plates silica gel 60, F-254. NMR spectra were recorded in 5 mm Norell NMR tubes on a VNMRS 600 MHz spectrometer (600 MHz for ¹H; 150 MHz for ¹³C, Varian, Inc., Palo Alto, CA, USA) Bruker Ascend 400 (400 MHz for ¹H; 100 MHz for ¹³C) in CDCl₃ as solvent. Coupling constants (J) were recorded in Hertz with multiplicities explained by the following abbreviations: s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, q = quartet, dd = doublet of doublets, hept = heptet, m = multiplet. Deuterated solvent for NMR measurements CDCl₃ was purchased from Eurisotop. Cyclic voltammograms and differential pulse voltammetry were recorded using a CH Instruments CHI660E electrochemical workstation using 5 mM solutions of the studied derivatives in 0.1 M TBAPF₆ in acetonitrile. Solutions were handled and stored under inert conditions prior to measurements. Electrochemistry experiments were performed using a three-electrode system, consisting of Glassy carbon as the working electrode, Ag/AgNO₃ (0.01 M in 0.1 M TBAPF₆ in acetonitrile contained in a glass tube fitted with a porous Vycor glass frit) as reference electrode and Pt wire as a counter electrode. All electrodes were well separated by porous frits. The measurements were carried out in inert atmosphere (Argon), sealing of the three-electrode system using septa and keeping an over pressure using a Schlenk line. Electronic absorption spectra were recorded using Agilent 8453 UV-vis diode array absorption spectrometer (190-1100 nm). Photoluminescence spectra were recorded using a Fluoromax 3 plus spectrofluorometer (Horiba) equipped with a Hamamatsu R13456 red-sensitive photomultiplier tube. High-resolution mass spectroscopy was measured using Orbitrap Thermo Scientific Velos pro with heated electrospray ionization (capillary temperature 350 °C, source heater temperature 300 °C, mass range 80–600 m/z, full scan, positive polarity, resolution 120000) or APPI/APCI (capillary temperature 290 °C). Melting points were measured using a

Melting Point M-656 apparatus (Büchi). 9-bromo-10-methoxyanthracene¹ and methyl 10-bromoanthracene-9-carboxylate² were prepared according to previously reported procedures.

2. Syntheses

2.1. Synthesis of 9-Bromo-10-nitroanthracene

Sodium nitrate (0.442 g, 5.20 mmol) was added portion wise over 30 min to a solution of 9-bromoanthracene (1.28 g, 5.00 mmol) in a mixture of trifluoroacetic acid (30 mL) and acetic anhydride (50 mL). The reaction mixture was then stirred for an additional 2 h. The reaction mixture was poured into ice-water (400 mL) containing concentrated H₂SO₄ (3 mL) and stirred overnight to ensure complete hydrolysis of excess acetic anhydride. The resulting precipitate was collected by filtration and washed thoroughly with water. Purification by column chromatography (petroleum ether followed by CH₂Cl₂ as eluent) afforded 9-Bromo-10-nitroanthracene (600 mg, 40%) as brown-yellow solid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.67–8.60 (m, 2H), 7.91–7.89 (m, 2H), 7.73–7.65 (m, 4H) ppm. Obtained data are in good agreement with literature.³

2.2. Synthesis of 5-*tert*-Butoxycarbonyl-5,10-dihydrophenazine (**Boc-DHP**)

To an 80-mL Schlenk flask, 5,10-dihydrophenazine (2.07 g, 11.4 mmol), 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP, 284.5 mg, 2.33 mmol), di-*tert*-butyl dicarbonate (Boc₂O, 3.02 g, 13.8 mmol), and THF (40 ml) were added, and the mixture was stirred for 20 h at 40 °C. After cooling to room temperature, the reaction mixture was filtered. The solvent was removed under vacuum, and the residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel with hexanes/CH₂Cl₂ = 1/1 and then with hexanes/EtOAc = 5/1 to give **3** (1.79 g, 56%) as a white solid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.40 (d, 2H, *J* = 7.8 Hz), 7.02 (ddd, 2H, *J* = 7.8, 7.5, 1.4 Hz), 6.92 (ddd, 2H, *J* = 7.8, 7.8, 1.4 Hz), 6.69 (dd, 2H, *J* = 7.8, 1.4 Hz), 5.73 (s, 1H), 1.51 (s, 9H) ppm. Obtained data are in good agreement with literature.⁴

2.3. Synthesis of *tert*-butyl 10-(anthracen-9-yl) phenazine-5(10H)-carboxylate (**Boc-DHP1**)

In a 100 ml Schlenk flask, compound **3** (400 mg, 1.416 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), 9-bromoanthracene (364.28 mg, 1.416 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), sodium *tert*-butoxide (626.38 mg, 6.516 mmol, 4.6 equiv.), Pd(OAc)₂ (22mg, 0.099 mmol, 0.07 equiv.), and [tBu₃PH]BF₄ (57 mg, 0.198 mmol, 0.14 equiv.) were combined. The flask was evacuated and backfilled with argon (three cycles). Dry toluene (12.5 mL) was added, and the reaction mixture was heated to reflux at 110 °C for 24 h. After completion, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and filtered through a short pad of Celite. The filtrate was concentrated, and the crude product was purified by column chromatography (ethyl acetate/hexanes = 5:95) to afford the desired product as a yellow solid (570 mg, 88 %). ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.64 (s, 1H), 8.13 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.91 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 7.51 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 4H), 7.40 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H), 6.91 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H), 6.72 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 5.89 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 2H), 1.59 (s, 9H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 153.59, 140.93, 132.52, 130.46, 130.29, 128.14, 127.96, 127.09, 126.02 – 125.63, 123.76, 120.70, 114.32, 81.82, 77.00, 28.29 ppm.

2.4. Synthesis of *tert*-butyl 10-(10-nitroanthracen-9-yl) phenazine-5(10H)-carboxylate (**Boc-DHP2**)

In a 100 mL Schlenk flask, compound **3** (300 mg, 1.062 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), 9-Bromo-10-nitroanthracene (321mg, 1.062 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), sodium *tert*-butoxide (468 mg, 4.876 mmol, 4.6 equiv.), Pd(OAc)₂ (17 mg, 0.074 mmol, 0.07 equiv.), and [tBu₃PH]BF₄ (43 mg, 0.148 mmol, 0.14

equiv.) were combined. The flask was evacuated and backfilled with argon (three cycles). Dry toluene (12.5 ml) was added, and the reaction mixture was heated to reflux at 110 °C for 24 h. After completion, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and filtered through a short pad of Celite. The filtrate was concentrated, and the crude product was purified by column chromatography (ethyl acetate/hexanes = 5:95) to afford the desired product as a yellow solid (492mg, 92%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.05–7.98 (m, 4H), 7.71–7.66 (m, 2H), 7.55–7.47 (m, 2H), 6.96 (t, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H), 6.76 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 5.86 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H), 1.60 (s, 9H) ppm.

2.5. Synthesis of *tert*-butyl 10-(10-methoxyanthracen-9-yl) phenazine-5(10H)-carboxylate (**Boc-DHP3**)

In a 100 mL Schlenk flask, *tert*-butyl phenazine-5(10H)-carboxylate (282 mg, 1 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), 9-bromo-10-methoxyanthracene (287mg, 1 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), sodium *tert*-butoxide (442 mg, 4.6 mmol, 4.6 equiv.), Pd(TFA)₂ (23.3 mg, 0.07 mmol, 0.07 equiv.), and [tBu₃PH]BF₄ (40.6 mg, 0.14 mmol, 0.14 equiv.) were combined. The flask was evacuated and backfilled with argon (three cycles). Dry toluene (15 mL) was added, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 h and then cooled to room temperature. The solvent was removed, and the residue was purified by column chromatography on SiO₂ (ethyl acetate/hexanes = 5:95) to afford *tert*-butyl 10-(10-methoxyanthracen-9-yl) phenazine-5(10H)-carboxylate (453 mg, 93 %) as yellow solid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.43 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 7.90 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.58–7.48 (m, 3H), 7.39 (ddd, *J* = 13.9, 7.4, 4.1 Hz, 2H), 6.95–6.87 (m, 2H), 6.77–6.69 (m, 2H), 5.91 (dd, *J* = 8.2, 1.1 Hz, 2H), 4.28 (s, 3H), 1.59 (s, 9H) ppm.

2.6. Synthesis of *tert*-butyl 10-(10-(methoxycarbonyl)anthracen-9-yl)phenazine-5(10H)-carboxylate (**Boc-DHP4**)

In a 100 mL Schlenk flask, *tert*-butyl phenazine-5(10H)-carboxylate (423 mg, 1.5 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), methyl 10-bromoanthracene-9-carboxylate (590 mg, 1.87 mmol, 1.25 equiv.), sodium *tert*-butoxide (663 mg, 6.9 mmol, 4.6 equiv.), Pd(TFA)₂ (33.2 mg, 0.1 mmol, 0.07 equiv.), and [tBu₃PH]BF₄ (61 mg, 0.21 mmol, 0.14 equiv.) were combined. The flask was evacuated and backfilled with argon (three cycles). Dry toluene (25 mL) was added, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 h and then cooled to room temperature. The solvent was removed, and the residue was purified by column chromatography on SiO₂ (ethyl acetate/hexanes = 10:90) to afford *tert*-

butyl 10-(10-(methoxycarbonyl)anthracen-9-yl)phenazine-5(10H)-carboxylate (681 mg, 88 %) as yellow solid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.1 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.96 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.51 (dd, *J* = 8.0, 1.3 Hz, 2H), 7.42 (ddd, *J* = 8.8, 6.6, 1.0 Hz, 2H), 6.92 (td, *J* = 8.0, 1.3 Hz, 2H), 6.79–6.67 (m, 2H), 5.87 (dd, *J* = 8.2, 1.2 Hz, 2H), 4.26 (s, 3H), 1.59 (s, 9H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 169.8, 153.6, 140.7, 133.0, 129.9, 129.3, 127.9, 127.3, 126.1, 124.2, 121.1, 114.4, 82.0, 52.9, 28.3 ppm.

2.7. Synthesis of 5-(anthracen-9-yl)-10-(naphthalen-1-yl)-5,10-dihydrophenazine (1)

In a 100 mL round-bottom flask, compound 4 (459 mg, 1.00 mmol) was dissolved in dichloromethane (10 mL) under an argon atmosphere. Trifluoroacetic acid (TFA, 0.75 mL, 9.90 mmol) was added dropwise at room temperature, and the reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, and the resulting residue was neutralized with 1 M NaOH. The mixture was extracted with dichloromethane, and the organic layers were separated and concentrated to afford a dark pink solid, which was further dried under reduced pressure. The obtained solid was transferred to a 250 mL Schlenk flask, and 1-bromonaphthalene (0.65 mL, 0.96 mmol, 1 equiv.), Pd(OAc)₂ (15 mg, 0.067 mmol, 0.07 equiv.), tri-*tert*-butylphosphonium tetrafluoroborate (39 mg, 0.135 mmol, 0.14 equiv.), and sodium *tert*-butoxide (428 mg, 4.45 mmol, 4.6 equiv.) were added. The flask was evacuated and backfilled with argon (three cycles), and dry 1,4-dioxane (40 mL) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed at 101 °C for 48 h. After cooling to room temperature, the reaction mixture was filtered through a short pad of silica, and the crude product was purified by recrystallization (Toluene/Methanol = 1:3) to afford the desired product as an orange solid (177mg, 38%).

2.8. Synthesis of 5-(anthracen-9-yl)-10-(naphthalen-2-yl)-5,10-dihydrophenazine (2)

In a 100 mL round-bottom flask, compound **4** (459 mg, 1.00 mmol) was dissolved in dichloromethane (10 mL) under an argon atmosphere. Trifluoroacetic acid (TFA, 0.75 mL, 9.90 mmol) was added dropwise at room temperature, and the reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, and the resulting residue was neutralized with 1 M NaOH. The mixture was extracted with dichloromethane, and the organic layers were separated and concentrated to afford a dark pink solid, which was further dried under reduced pressure. The obtained solid was transferred to a 250 mL Schlenk flask, and 2-bromonaphthalene (201 mg, 0.96 mmol, 1 equiv.), Pd(OAc)₂ (15 mg, 0.067 mmol, 0.07 equiv.), tri-*tert*-butylphosphonium tetrafluoroborate (39 mg, 0.135 mmol, 0.14 equiv.), and sodium *tert*-butoxide (428 mg, 4.45 mmol, 4.6 equiv.) were added. The flask was evacuated and backfilled with argon (three cycles), and dry 1,4-dioxane (40 mL) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed at 101 °C for 48 h. After cooling to room temperature, the reaction mixture was filtered through a short pad of silica, and the crude product was purified by recrystallization (Toluene/Methanol = 1:3) to afford the desired product as a dark yellow solid (279mg, 60%).

2.9. Synthesis of 5,10-di(anthracen-9-yl)-5,10-dihydrophenazine (3)

In a 100 mL round-bottom flask, compound **4** (458.56 mg, 1.00 mmol) was dissolved in dichloromethane (10 mL) under an argon atmosphere. Trifluoroacetic acid (TFA, 0.75 mL, 9.90 mmol) was added dropwise at room temperature, and the reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, and the resulting residue was neutralized with 1 M NaOH. The mixture was extracted with dichloromethane, and the organic layers were separated and concentrated to afford a dark pink solid, which was further dried under reduced pressure. The obtained solid was transferred to a 250 mL Schlenk flask, and 9-bromoanthracene (244 mg, 0.95 mmol), Pd(OAc)₂ (15 mg, 0.066 mmol), tri-*tert*-butylphosphonium tetrafluoroborate (38 mg, 0.133 mmol), and sodium *tert*-butoxide (420 mg, 4.37 mmol) were added. The flask was evacuated and backfilled with argon (three cycles), and dry 1,4-dioxane (40 mL) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed at 101 °C for 48 h. After cooling to room temperature, the reaction mixture

was filtered through a short pad of silica, and the crude product was purified by recrystallization (Toluene/Methanol = 1:3) to afford the desired product as a brown solid (122mg, 23%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.77 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 4H), 8.65 (s, 2H), 8.18 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 4H), 7.71–7.64 (m, 4H), 7.62–7.56 (m, 4H), 6.02 (dd, *J* = 5.9, 3.4 Hz, 4H), 5.24 (dd, *J* = 5.9, 3.5 Hz, 4H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 136.51, 134.28, 133.30, 131.15, 130.29, 129.41, 127.95, 127.52, 126.10, 124.14, 121.40 ppm. HRMS (HESI): *m/z* [M+H]⁺ calcd for C₄₀H₂₇N₂: 535.2153, found: 535.2168.

2.10. Synthesis of 5,10-bis(10-nitroanthracen-9-yl)-5,10-dihydrophenazine (4)

In a 100 mL round-bottom flask, compound **Boc-DHP2** (450 mg, 0.893 mmol, 1 equiv.) was dissolved in dichloromethane (10 mL) under an argon atmosphere. Trifluoroacetic acid (TFA, 0.68 mL, 8.891 mmol, 9.95 equiv.) was added dropwise at room temperature, and the reaction mixture

was stirred for 3 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, and the resulting residue was neutralized with 1 M NaOH. The mixture was extracted with dichloromethane, and the organic layers were separated and concentrated to afford a dark pink solid, which was further dried under reduced pressure. The obtained solid was transferred to a 250 mL Schlenk flask, and 9-Bromo-10-

nitroanthracene (264 mg, 0.875 mmol, 1 equiv.), Pd(OAc)₂ (14 mg, 0.061 mmol, 0.07 equiv.), tri-*tert*-butylphosphonium tetrafluoroborate (35 mg, 0.122 mmol, 0.14 equiv.), and sodium *tert*-butoxide (386 mg, 4.02 mmol, 4.6 equiv.) were added. The flask was evacuated and backfilled with argon (three cycles), and dry 1,4-dioxane (40 mL) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed at 101 °C for 48 h. After cooling to room temperature, the reaction mixture was filtered through a short pad of silica, and the crude product was purified by recrystallization (Toluene/Methanol = 1:3) to afford the desired product as a brown solid (166 mg, 29%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.86–8.80 (m, 4H), 8.11–8.07 (m, 4H), 7.80–7.76 (m, 8H), 6.13 (dd, *J* = 6.3, 3.3 Hz, 4H), 5.28 (dd, *J* = 5.8, 3.6 Hz, 4H) ppm.

2.11. Synthesis of 5,10-bis(10-methoxyanthracen-9-yl)-5,10-dihydrophenazine (5)

To a solution of **Boc-DHP3** (488 mg, 1.00 mmol) in dichloromethane (10 mL) trifluoroacetic acid (0.77 mL, 10 mmol, 10 equiv.) was added dropwise at room temperature under an argon atmosphere, and the reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, and the resulting residue was dissolved in DCM (30 mL) and 1 M NaOH (50 mL was added). The mixture was extracted with dichloromethane (3 x 30 mL), the organic layers were dried and concentrated under reduced pressure to afford a dark purple solid, which was further dried in vacuo. To the obtained solid were added 9-bromo-10-methoxyanthracene (287 mg, 1 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), sodium *tert*-butoxide (442 mg, 4.6 mmol, 4.6 equiv.), Pd(TFA)₂ (23 mg, 0.07 mmol, 0.07 equiv.), and [tBu₃PH]BF₄ (41 mg, 0.14 mmol, 0.14 equiv.) were combined. The flask was evacuated and backfilled with argon (three cycles). Dry dioxane (40 mL) was added, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 48 h and then cooled to room temperature. The reaction mixture was filtered through a short pad of silica, and the crude product was purified by recrystallization (Toluene/Methanol = 1:3) to afford the desired product as a red solid (220 mg, 37 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.76 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 4H), 8.48 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 4H), 7.70–7.60 (m, 8H), 6.03 (dd, *J* = 5.8, 3.4 Hz, 4H), 5.26 (dd, *J* = 5.7, 3.5 Hz, 4H) 4.48 (s, 6H) ppm.

2.12. Synthesis of dimethyl 10,10'-(phenazine-5,10-diyl)bis(anthracene-9-carboxylate) (6)

To a solution of **7** (516 mg, 1.00 mmol) in dichloromethane (10 mL) trifluoroacetic acid (0.77 mL, 10 mmol, 10 equiv.) was added dropwise at room temperature under an argon atmosphere, and the reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, and the resulting residue was dissolved in DCM (30 mL) and 1 M NaOH (50 mL was added). The mixture was extracted with dichloromethane (3 x 30 mL), the organic layers were dried and concentrated under reduced pressure to afford a dark pink solid, which was further dried in vacuo. To the obtained solid were added methyl 10-bromoanthracene-9-carboxylate (313 mg, 1 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), sodium *tert*-butoxide (442 mg, 4.6 mmol, 4.6 equiv.), Pd(TFA)₂ (23 mg, 0.07 mmol, 0.07 equiv.), and [tBu₃PH]BF₄ (41 mg, 0.14 mmol, 0.14 equiv.) were combined. The flask was evacuated and backfilled with argon (three cycles). Dry dioxane (40 mL) was added, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 48 h and then cooled to room temperature. The reaction mixture was filtered through a short pad of silica, and the crude product was purified by recrystallization (Toluene/Methanol = 1:3) to afford the desired product as a brown solid (312 mg, 48 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.15 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 4H), 7.76 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 4H), 7.64–7.39 (m, 8H), 6.13 (dd, *J* = 6.3, 3.3 Hz, 4H), 5.28 (dd, *J* = 5.8, 3.6 Hz, 4H) 4.28 (s, 6H) ppm.

2.13. Synthesis of 5-(10-methoxyanthracen-9-yl)-10-(10-nitroanthracen-9-yl)-5,10-dihydrophenazine (7)

To a solution of **5** (503 mg, 1.00 mmol) in dichloromethane (10 mL) trifluoroacetic acid (0.77 mL, 10 mmol, 10 equiv.) was added dropwise at room temperature under an argon atmosphere, and the reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, and the resulting residue was dissolved in DCM (30 mL) and 1 M NaOH (50 mL was added). The mixture was extracted with dichloromethane (3 x 30 mL), the organic layers were dried and concentrated under reduced pressure to afford a dark purple solid, which was further dried in vacuo. To the obtained solid were added 9-bromo-10-methoxyanthracene (287mg, 1 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), sodium *tert*-butoxide (442 mg, 4.6 mmol, 4.6 equiv.), Pd(TFA)₂ (23 mg, 0.07 mmol, 0.07 equiv.), and

[^tBu₃PH]BF₄ (40.6 mg, 0.14 mmol, 0.14 equiv.) were combined. The flask was evacuated and backfilled with argon (three cycles). Dry dioxane (40 mL) was added, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 48 h and then cooled to room temperature. The reaction mixture was filtered through a short pad of silica, and the crude product was purified by recrystallization (Toluene/Methanol = 1:3) to afford the desired product as a brown solid (164 mg, 27 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 9.04 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 2H), 8.87 (d, *J* = 9.6 Hz, 2H), 8.71 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 2H), 8.48 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 7.69–7.60 (m, 8H), 6.03 (dd, *J* = 5.8, 3.4 Hz, 4H), 5.26 (dd, *J* = 5.7, 3.5 Hz, 4H) 4.31 (s, 3H) ppm.

3. Results

3.1. Cyclic voltammogram of synthesized *N,N*-diaryl dihydrophenazine derivatives

Figure S2. Cyclic voltammogram of DHPAN-1 and DHPAN-2, in DCM with 0.1 M Bu_4NPF_6 as the supporting electrolyte, Ag/AgNO_3 as the reference electrode, and a Pt wire as the counter electrode and a scan rate at 100 mV/s

Figure S3. Cyclic voltammogram of DHPA and DHPA- NO_2 , in DCM with 0.1 M Bu_4NPF_6 as the supporting electrolyte, Ag/AgNO_3 as the reference electrode, and a Pt wire as the counter electrode and a scan rate at 100 mV/s

Figure S4. Cyclic voltammogram of DHPA-OMe and DHPA-OMeNO₂, DHPA-COOMe in DCM with 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ as the supporting electrolyte, Ag/AgNO₃ as the reference electrode, and a Pt wire as the counter electrode and a scan rate at 100 mV/s.

3.2. NMR spectra

Figure S10. ^1H NMR spectrum of *tert*-butyl 10-(10-nitroanthracen-9-yl) phenazine-5(10H)-carboxylate (**Boc-DHP2**).

Figure S11. ^1H NMR spectrum *tert*-butyl 10-(10-(methoxycarbonyl)anthracen-9-yl)phenazine-5(10H)-carboxylate (**Boc-DHP3**).

Figure S.12 ¹H NMR spectrum of *tert*-butyl 10-(10-(methoxycarbonyl)anthracen-9-yl)phenazine-5(10H)-carboxylate (**Boc-DHP4**).

Figure S13. ¹H NMR spectrum of 5-(anthracen-9-yl)-10-(naphthalen-1-yl)-5,10-dihydrophenazine (**1**).

Figure S14. ¹H NMR spectrum of 5,10-di(anthracen-9-yl)-5,10-dihydrophenazine (3).

Figure S15. ¹H NMR spectrum of 5,10-bis(10-nitroanthracen-9-yl)-5,10-dihydrophenazine (4).

Figure S16. ¹H NMR spectrum of dimethyl 10,10'-(phenazine-5,10-diyl)bis(anthracene-9-carboxylate) (**6**).

4. References

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